
**Evaluation of pilot
demonstration and policy
recommendations & briefing**

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Administrative Information

Basic information on the DyMoN project and the present deliverable:

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Purpose of the document

This deliverable gives a detailed view of the evaluation of the DyMoN pilot demonstration in Salzburg, Austria (“Science City Aktiv Mobil”), including statistical analysis of effects of situation-aware digital nudging and questionnaire feedback of participants. Furthermore, it includes the DyMoN policy recommendations and a policy briefing that are based on a review of the literature on related topics and the project’s own empirical research and experiences. The deliverable is connected to other deliverables that provide more details on the DyMoN approach, tools and methods: The “Nudging Review” (D2.1a) explains the theoretical foundations of the behavioural interventions that were used in a functional proof of concept and the pilot demonstration. The deliverable “Nudging Repository” (D2.2a) describes the large set of nudges some of which were tested in the pilot demonstration. “DyMoN Data Hub, Tools and Data Processing Model” (D3.1) presents the structure and technical implementation of the Data Hub for situation-aware nudges and describes the data integrated for such nudges. “DyMoN Proof of Concept demonstration” (D4.1) includes a more detailed description of the pilot demonstration in Salzburg, including lessons learned and suggestions for good practices. The “Evaluation Plan” (D5.1) provides the methods for the evaluation of the pilot, including the questionnaires for the participants.

Executive summary

The project carried out a pilot demonstration over the course of two months in Salzburg, Austria (“Science City Aktiv Mobil”). The goals were to demonstrate the technical feasibility of the DyMoN framework and gain insights into the effectiveness of situation-aware digital nudging for sustainable mobility. The technical proof of concept was a success as the implemented research infrastructure with the Data Hub, the Nudging Repository and process of situation-aware nudging worked as expected. Regarding the effectiveness of the situation-aware nudges no definite insights could be abstracted due to the study design and an insufficient sample size. However, qualitative feedback of participants showed that events accompanying the sustainable mobility campaign together with the nudges were the most motivating aspects. Nudges regarding health information, general motivation for sustainable mobility and climate information were found to be most motivating. Thus, situation-aware nudging using the DyMoN framework is technically feasible and should best be used in conjunction with a sustainable mobility campaign, including events for participants, and highlight health and climate related benefits of sustainable mobility.

The DyMoN policy recommendations for appropriate application of digital nudging to promote sustainable mobility of citizens position such interventions in the context of the city challenges of contributing to climate and environmental targets regarding CO₂ emissions, air quality, pollutants and noise from urban mobility. The 15 DyMoN recommendations concern city policies and plans for sustainable mobility, behaviour change methods for promoting use of sustainable mobility modes, supporting ICT and data services, and related legal and ethical aspects. For each of these four themes relevant background is given, followed by the respective recommendations. Stakeholders in sustainable mobility addressed are city policy makers, managers of mobility infrastructure and services, providers of other services (e.g., behavioural intervention methods, ICT and data services), and citizens who use such services. The Policy Briefing highlights the relevance of digital nudging for tackling city sustainable mobility challenges, introduces the DyMoN approach of situation-aware digital nudging, and provides the recommendations for such nudging for different stakeholders.

1 Evaluation of the pilot demonstration in Salzburg

1.1 Implementation of the pilot

We briefly introduce the DyMoN pilot demonstration in Salzburg, Austria, implemented in the “Science City Aktiv Mobil” campaign.

1.1.1 Location and target group

The DyMoN demonstration took place in a neighborhood in Salzburg, called Science City Itzling.¹ The activity was coordinated and led by Salzburg Research and carried out in cooperation with University of Salzburg (Department of Geoinformatics) and Trafficon.

Employees of companies located at Science City Itzling took part in the sustainable mobility campaign “Science City Aktiv Mobil”. The target group was people who are currently often using their car to get to work, but who could use more sustainable, active modes of transport (walking, bicycling) or public transport.

The project team reached out to several companies, which distributed information about the campaign to their employees. In addition, posters were put up around the Science City Salzburg with a link for the campaign registration page (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Poster with information about the campaign.

For the registration, a welcome page was set up on the project website, which offered all the necessary information and details for participants to join and served as first contact point also with companies that were interested in taking part (see Figure 2).

¹ <https://www.techno-z.at/en/location-and-service/university-and-research/>

Figure 2: Screenshots of the registration page (<https://dymon.eu/science-city-aktiv-mobil-anmeldung/>).

1.1.2 Supporting events

Several activities accompanied the campaign to provide a meaningful setting for the participants and to develop a sense of community which are important for the success of such campaigns (Luger-Bazinger & Hornung-Prähauser, 2021). The campaign started on the 23rd of March 2023 with a kick-off event to inform people who were interested to participate, including a lunch for networking. Furthermore, a bicycle repair station was provided supporting people in using their bicycle for commuting to work. Another event was a talk of Dr. Birgit Böhm from the Technical University Munich on how physical activity in everyday life is beneficial for the cardiovascular system and overall well-being, and how a change from car use to sustainable forms of commuting can support a healthy lifestyle. At the end of the campaign, on the 1st of June 2023, a community picnic was organized to celebrate the achieved results.

1.1.3 Campaign app

In the campaign, Pandocs², an Austrian app, was used to interact with the DyMoN system and receive nudge messages. Pandocs has been designed to motivate users in a playful way towards a healthy and sustainable lifestyle. This includes challenges for fitness, mental well-being and nutrition. The advantage of not using an app specifically for mobility behaviour is

² <https://www.pandocs.com/en/>

that the Pandocs app offers more content for a broader audience than an app that is, for example, already geared towards bicycling.

On the campaign registration page (see Figure 2) the participants received a detailed description on how to download the app and connect their individual user account with the group “Science City Aktiv Mobil”. After doing this, the participants could see on their smartphone the content that was prepared for the campaign and receive digital nudges.

In the Pandocs app, a new category for active mobility was introduced for the campaign (see Figure 3):

Figure 3: Screenshots of campaign content as seen by the users of the Pandocs app.

Here, the participants could collect gamified points for sustainable commutes to and from work, receive information about the DyMoN dashboard and links to online surveys (see below). Participants could decide for which kind of sustainable mobility mode they wanted to receive motivational nudges and could switch between modes if needed. The content of the nudge messages was adjusted automatically.

1.1.4 Demonstration procedure

In the demonstration a number of digital nudges from the nudging repository were tested; see D2.2a “Nudging Repository” (DyMoN 2023a/b), and for the technical implementation, D3.1 “DyMoN data hub” (DyMoN 2023c) and Loidl et al. (2023). For the demonstration the nudges were translated into German and shortened to fit the requirements of the Pandocs app (for examples see Figure 4).

Figure 4: Examples of nudges sent as notifications to Pandocs app users.

The participants received two nudges per day, one in the morning, one in the evening, except on Saturday and Sunday. On Sunday, a notification was only sent in the evening. Nudges were sent from 23 March to 23 of May 2023.

The prove of concept demonstration involved two groups of participants. Participants in the intervention group received situation-aware nudges, which took account of situational factors such as weather or traffic conditions. The control group received only generic nudges with no situational component (see also D5.1 “Project Evaluation and Impact Plan”, DyMoN 2023e).

In the Pandocs app group “Science City Aktiv Mobil”, we provided “challenges” that only campaign participants could see. Here the participants could confirm that they commuted to work with sustainable mobility modes by finishing the associated challenge (“Radl-Tag” for bike, “Gut zu Fuß” for walking and “Bus und Bahn” for public transport). For this they received “Lebenspunkte” (life points) from the gamification system of Pandocs.

Over the course of the campaign, participants were asked to fill out two online surveys, one at the beginning and one at the end of the campaign. These surveys were also designed as “challenges” for which participants could get points after finishing a survey, similar to the mobility challenges. Accessing information about the Dashboard was also presented as a challenge. In addition, participants could answer a short quiz about the dashboard to gain some extra points.

1.2 Results of the pilot

1.2.1 Participants

The sample consisted of 53 participants in total, 21 male and 32 female. None of the participants identified as diverse. Participants were recruited in the Science City Itzling, Salzburg with the help of flyers and other information material, which was distributed in the local companies.

Participants were randomly attributed to either control (n=25) or intervention (n=28) group. In the control group, gender was evenly attributed with male=13, female=12. In the intervention group however, there were about three times more women than men (male=8, female=20) (see Figure 5).

Mean age of the participants was $M=40.74$ ($SD=10.54$), ranging from $min=24$ to $max=60$.

Figure 5: Number of participants per group and per gender.

Figure 6: Total frequency of age groups.

Mobility opportunities: 92% of participants reported that public transport would be available for their commute to work. 87% reported they had the opportunity to commute by bike, while only around half of the sample (57%) could use their car. Only 45% reported to be able to walk to work (see Figure 7).

Mobility preferences: For their preferred modes to receive nudges for, 85% of participants chose the bike, 42% chose public transport and 40% chose walking (see Figure 8). Some of the participants added multiple modes to receive motivation in.

Figure 7: Opportunity to use different modes of transport for commutes to work and Preference for which mode to receive motivational nudges.

Figure 8: Preferred mode for receiving mobility nudges.

1.2.2 Analysis of completed challenges

In total, the participants gained 45.907 so called “Health Points” using the app Pandocs. 15.528 points were earned by completing challenges in the app. Of those 5.592 points were earned by completing mobility challenges by commuting to work with sustainable modes of transport.

Female participants on average earned more points ($M = 382.26$, $SD = 607.89$, $min = 2$, $max = 2480$) than male participants ($M = 178.24$, $SD = 189.09$, $min = 4$, $max = 757$). But most of those points were earned outside of Science City Aktiv Mobil, as female participants completed less mobility challenges ($M = 29.23$, $SD = 24.09$, $min = 0$, $max = 108$) than male participants ($M = 43.65$, $SD = 56.62$, $min = 2$, $max = 238$).

Participants in our intervention group (regardless of gender) earned on average earned more points ($M = 396.16$, $SD = 649.68$, $min = 5$, $max = 2480$) than participants in the control group ($M = 216.35$, $SD = 269.48$, $min = 2$, $max = 1033$). The control group however completed more mobility challenges ($M = 38.26$, $SD = 51.18$, $min = 0$, $max = 238$) than the intervention group ($M = 30.72$, $SD = 22.99$, $min = 2$, $max = 108$). A detailed view on earned points and completed mobility challenges can be found in table 1 and 2.

Gender	Group	Mean points	SD	Min	Max
female	control	228.33	323.26	2	1033
female	intervention	479.47	725.44	10	2480
male	control	203.27	210.85	4	757
male	intervention	132.33	146.94	5	382

Table 1: Earned points via challenges in Pandocs by gender and group.

Gender	Group	Mean points	SD	Min	Max
female	control	23.17	23.1	0	72
female	intervention	33.05	24.53	2	108
male	control	54.73	67.85	2	238
male	intervention	23.33	16.91	4	48

Table 2: Completed mobility challenges after sustainable commutes by gender and group.

A t-test comparing the differences between the gender in the average earned points showed a significant difference (mean difference = -204.02, $t(39.23) = 1.72$, $p = 0.09$ (2-tailed)).

The difference between gender in average completed mobility challenges however is not significant (mean difference = 14.42, $t(19.23) = -1$, $p = 0.33$ (2-tailed)).

For the difference between intervention and control group, neither the earned points (mean difference = 179.81, $t(32.57) = -1.27$, $p = 0.21$ (2-tailed)), nor the completed mobility challenges (mean difference = -7.54, $t(29.98) = 0.65$, $p = 0.52$ (2-tailed)) were statistically significant.

Age was significantly correlated with earned points ($r = 0.43$, $t(46) = 3.2$, $p < 0.01$ (2-tailed)), as well as with completed mobility challenges ($r = 0.42$, $t(46) = 3.16$, $p < 0.01$ (2-tailed)). Older participants have earned more points and completed more mobility challenges on average than younger participants (see Figure 9)

Figure 9: Scatterplots showing the relationship between age and earned points, as well as age and completed mobility challenges.

Figure 10 and 11 show that over the course of the campaign there was a slight decline in earned points (Figure 10) as well as completed mobility challenges (Figure 11).

Figure 10: Earned points from challenges over time.

Figure 11: Completed mobility challenges over time.

1.2.3 Active users over time

Figure 12: count of active users over the course of the campaign.

Figure 12 visualizes the count of active individual users per day. The same pattern can be observed here as already seen in Figure 10. The participation rate dropped over the course of the campaign. Also, most participants only used the app on workdays, which explains the drops on the graph. It is important to note that only those who finished a challenge on that day were included in this graph. Interactions without a finished challenge could not be logged.

Figure 13: count of active users per week over the campaign.

Figure 13 shows that in the second week, most individual users recorded some activity in the app.

1.2.4 Feedback on nudges and the campaign

Figure 14: Feedback on Science City Aktiv Mobil. Feedback was given on a 5-point Likert Scale. (0 = "Does not apply", 4 = "Does apply").

We asked participants for insights on their mobility awareness and choices, and for feedback on the campaign as well on the used nudges.

In a first online survey, we used the following feedback variables:

- fb_ 1 = Science City Aktiv Mobil has motivated me to think about different modes of transport
- fb_ 2 = The campaign has shown me new sides of environmentally friendly means of transport
- fb_ 3 = For the campaign I chose the car less
- fb_ 4 = For the campaign I chose more sustainable modes of transport
- fb_ 5 = Through Science City Aktiv Mobil I wanted to use more sustainable modes of transport

Feedback via self-report on the campaign showed that on average, even though people wanted to use more sustainable mobility modes (fb_5, M = 1.8), and people were motivated to think about different modes of transport (fb_1, M = 1.7), they did not actually chose the car less as mobility choice (fb_3, M = 1.0) (see Figure 14).

Figure 15: Comparison of how often people reported to use the car before the campaign(left) and during the campaign (right).

Of the participants that had access to a car for their commute to work and who filled out our questionnaires (N=10), more people reported to have never used the car to commute to work during the campaign than before the campaign (see Figure 15). The percentage of people who reported to use the car rarely or often is lower after the campaign than before. It can be assumed that people who have access to a car but don't necessarily have to use it were motivated by our campaign to not use the car at all and rather use sustainable mobility modes.

Figure 16: Comparison of which mobility nudges were considered the most motivating by participants with access to a car for their commute.

Participants who had access to a car found nudges about health information (M = 2.7), about climate information (M = 2.5) and nudges containing motivation (M = 2.2) the most motivating. (Figure 16)

Concerning all participants, a similar pattern emerged, with nudges about health information (M = 2.20), containing motivation (M = 2.15) and about climate information (M = 2.10) being the most motivating. As seen in Figure 11 however, there is a difference between the genders in our sample. Female participants found all nudges more motivating than male participants. (Figure 17)

Figure 17: Comparison of which nudges were considered most motivating by all participants and split by gender.

The events were found to be the most motivating part of Science City Aktiv Mobil ($M = 2.35$), followed by the nudges ($M = 2.1$). Notably, female participants deemed all aspects of the campaign more motivation than male participants. (see Figure 18).

Figure 18: Comparison of how motivating different aspects of Science City Aktiv Mobil by gender.

1.3 Technical feasibility

The nudging process during the field study was technically implemented using the Data Hub and the Nudging API. The Data hub collected and stored all necessary static and real-time data and calculated individual nudges per request (see D3.1 “DyMoN data hub” (DyMoN 2023c)). The Nudging API was an intermediary point providing secure access to the Data Hub, scheduling nudge calculation, and sending nudges to Pandocs mobile application, an external end-client. In order to prove the technical feasibility of the framework, we check whether the Data Hub performed according to the field study design.

We have collected the logs of nudge requests to the Data Hub. The logs file consists of anonymous input parameters of a user, situational context of a user, and nudge information calculated for a user, such as the timestamp of a request, user group, mode preferences, locational information, weather values, quality of infrastructure, and other environmental characteristics, as well as nudge id, nudge text and its situation awareness. Due to technical reasons that were not immediately noticed, the registration of the log file started a week later after the start of the field study.

In total there were 6,095 nudge requests made between the period of 28 of March – 23 May 2023. We have observed that some web requests were not satisfied, and no nudges were calculated based on the input parameters. Such cases occurred to users that were outside of the study area of Salzburg. Thus, 801 requests did not generate nudges and the total of 5294 calculated nudges consisted of 1785 situation-aware nudges and 3509 non-situation-aware nudges (Figure 19).

Figure 19: Number of nudges by situation awareness attribute.

The temporal distribution of nudges per day sent by the Data Hub is visualized in Figure 20. Requests were not received on Saturdays and there is a smaller number of requests on Sundays according to the field study design. Figure 21 shows the number of nudges received by Pandocs from the Data Hub. The numbers of sent and received nudges are the same as shown on both figures 20 and 21 except for additional mobility-related notifications issued by Pandocs on some dates.

Figure 20: Number of sent nudges by the Data Hub by date.

Figure 21: Number of responses received by Pandocs from the Data Hub by date.

Nudge requests were scheduled in the morning at 6:00 and in the evening at 20:00 by design. The Figure 22 below demonstrates its correct implementation, as nudge requests to the Data Hub were made exactly in these hours.

Figure 22: Total number of requests by hour.

In conclusion, it can be stated the Data Hub delivered the nudges according to the study design and worked properly throughout the investigation period.

1.4 Effects of situation-aware nudging

One of the aims of the study is to check whether the consideration of situational context for calculation of nudges improves their effectivity and consequently increases the number of sustainable trips. Situational context represents the environmental conditions around a participant in the moment a nudge is sent, or challenge is completed. The hypothesis states that situation-aware nudges sent to the intervention group will trigger more trips made by sustainable transport than non-situation-aware nudges sent to the control group.

We compared completed mobility challenges against situational context (weather, bikeability, walkability) of participants by user group. Mobility challenges are designed to ask users about their travel mode on that day (Figure 23). They are sent out to all users independently of their situational context and can be used to observe any shifts in travel choices due to nudging and hence track its effectivity.

Figure 23: Distribution of accepted mobility challenges by mode type and user group.

The boxplots in Figure 24 show the medium and quantile values of daily weather characteristics of challenges that were completed by two user groups. Daily weather values were computed as average air temperature, average precipitation, average wind speed and total duration of sunshine. While there is clear variability in weather context, the travel behaviour between two user groups seems to be similar. Based on the results of Kruskal-Wallis statistic (Table 3) there is not enough evidence to assume that the distributions by user type are nonidentical. The low number of observations and the applied statistical test do not allow any conclusions to be drawn about the effectiveness or differences between the user groups.

Figure 24: Distribution of accepted mobility challenges against daily weather values by user type.

Table 3: Kruskal-Wallis chi-squared statistic of challenges characterized by weather conditions indicating significance of difference between user groups.

Weather values	Bus & Train	Cycling to work today?	Good on foot
Temperature	0.1, $p > 0.05$	1.74, $p > 0.05$	0.1, $p > 0.05$
Precipitation	2.03, $p > 0.05$	0.33, $p > 0.05$	0.24, $p > 0.05$
Wind speed	1.25, $p > 0.05$	0.2, $p > 0.05$	1.62, $p > 0.05$
Sunshine duration	2.72, $p > 0.05$	$5.54 \cdot 10^{-6}$, $p > 0.05$	3.1, $p > 0.05$

Figures 25-28 show the daily distribution of accepted mobility challenges by type and user group against weather values. Table 3 shows Pearson’s correlation coefficients between challenges and weather values. We used values on weekdays to avoid untraced behaviour during the weekends, as the challenges and nudges are designed to influence the mode choice of utilitarian trips to work locations. There are a few significant and moderate relationships observed. In terms of temperature, there is a medium negative correlation with “Bus & Train” and “Cycling to work today?” challenges for the intervention group, $r=-0.43$ ($p<0.01$) and $r=-0.38$ ($p<0.5$) respectively. Wind speed is positively correlated with “Good on foot” challenges for the intervention group, $r=0.38$ ($p<0.5$). Sunshine duration values are negatively correlated with “Bus & Train” challenges for the control group ($r=-0.38$, $p<0.5$) and with “Good on foot” challenges for intervention group ($r=0.31$, $p<0.5$).

Figure 25: Distribution of accepted mobility challenges against daily average temperature by user type.

Figure 26: Distribution of accepted mobility challenges against daily average precipitation by user type.

Figure 27: Distribution of accepted mobility challenges against daily average wind speed by user type.

Figure 28: Distribution of accepted mobility challenges against daily sunshine duration by user type.

Table 4: Pearson’s correlation coefficients of the number of accepted challenges by type and user group against weather values by date.

Challenge type	User group	Temperature (r)	Precipitation(r)	Wind speed (r)	Sunshine duration (r)
Bus & Train	control	-0.27 ns	0.14 ns	0.06 ns	-0.38 *
Bus & Train	intervention	-0.43 **	0.11 ns	0.27 ns	-0.29 ns
Cycling to work today?	control	-0.14 ns	-0.04 ns	0.14 ns	-0.22 ns
Cycling to work today?	intervention	-0.38 *	-0.13 ns	0.29 ns	-0.2 ns
Good on foot	control	-0.07 ns	-0.06 ns	0.12 ns	-0.08 ns
Good on foot	intervention	-0.18 ns	-0.07 ns	0.38 *	-0.31 *

ns = not significant ($p > 0.05$), * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

To understand whether infrastructure influences the acceptance of mobility challenges, we tested the number of challenges per user group against three factors: walkability, bikeability and proximity to the closest public transport station (Figure 29). Walkability and bikeability are indices that indicate how suitable roads are for walking and cycling. Roads are assessed based on the type of pedestrian and bicycle infrastructure, speed limits, gradient, heterogeneity of an area around, closeness to green and water areas, etc. The calculation follows the method developed by Werner et.al (2022). Both factors are assessed for the neighbourhood of 400 m around participants’ home locations and along the home-work route. They range from 0.0 (low) to 1.0 (high). Another factor is proximity to public transport stops reflecting accessibility of public transport services within 400 m of participants’ home locations.

In case of accepted “Good on foot” challenges, distributions of walkability index in proximity from home location as well as the average walkability along a route to work are higher for the control group than the intervention group (Figure 29). This contrasts with the bikeability indices against “Cycling to work today?” challenges, where they are lower for the control group than for the intervention group. The distances to public transport stops are higher for the control group that accepted “Bus & Train” challenges in comparison to the intervention group, which lives closer to the public transport stations.

Figure 29: Distribution of accepted challenges and their walkability, bikeability, pt proximity.

Figure 30 shows the distribution of accepted bicycle challenges (“Cycling to work today?”) against the route distances to work locations by user group. The variability of distances as well as the median distance are higher for the intervention group than for the control group.

Figure 30: Distribution of accepted “Cycling to work?” challenges against the route distances that participants have taken to work locations.

1.5 Brief summary of the evaluation results

The demonstration of the technical feasibility of the DyMoN framework was successful as the implemented research infrastructure with the Nudging Repository, Data Hub and process of situation-aware nudging worked as expected. The infrastructure delivered the nudges according to the study design and worked properly throughout the investigation period.

The analysis of the nudging effects concerned completed mobility challenges, i.e., walk, cycle or use public transport to commute to work, self-reported by 53 pilot participants. These were separated in an intervention and a control group. The intervention group received situation-aware while the control group non-situation-aware nudge messages.

Across the participants 85% wished receiving nudges to use a bike for commuting, 42% public transport and 40% walking, thus quite some selected nudges for all three sustainable mobility modes. The intervention group reported more completed public transport and walking challenges, while the control group more completed cycling challenges, of which there were significantly more than for each of the other two sustainable mobility modes.

The analysis of the completed challenges regarding the influence of weather conditions, and nudges which did or did not take account of these (i.e. intervention versus control group), did not yield clear conclusions regarding their relative effectiveness. Some correlations between weather conditions and completed challenges could be found (e.g., cycling of members of the intervention group was more negatively affected by temperature), however overall, the mobility behaviour of the two groups appeared to be quite similar.

In addition, an analysis of accepted sustainable mobility challenges against availability of required infrastructure, i.e., walkability, bikeability and proximity to the closest public transport station, was conducted. Again, some differences between the intervention and the control group were found which can affect mobility choices. For example, members of the intervention group had a higher bikeability but also higher route distance to the workplace. Notably, this group completed many, but less cycling challenges than the control group. In conclusion, the analyses yielded interesting but not conclusive results for the higher effectiveness of situation-aware versus non-situation-aware nudges.

The questionnaire-based feedback of participants showed that events accompanying the sustainable mobility campaign together with the nudges were the most motivating aspects. Especially nudges concerning health benefits of active mobility (walk, cycle), positive climate effects, and general motivation for sustainable mobility were appreciated. Thus, situation-aware nudging using the DyMoN framework should best be used in conjunction with a sustainable mobility campaign, including community events for participants, and highlight health and climate related benefits of sustainable mobility.

2 DyMoN policy recommendations

This part of the deliverable presents the DyMoN recommendations on appropriate application of digital behaviour change interventions (nudging) for promoting sustainable mobility of citizens. The introduction positions such interventions in the context of the city challenges of contributing to climate and environmental targets regarding CO₂ emissions, air quality, pollutants and noise from urban mobility. Furthermore, the DyMoN approach of digital situation-aware nudging is explained.

The policy recommendations are based on a review of the literature on related topics and the project's own empirical research and experiences. The recommendations focus on the themes of city policies and plans for sustainable mobility, behaviour change methods for promoting use of sustainable mobility modes, supporting ICT and data services, and related legal and ethical issues.

2.1 City sustainable mobility challenges and the need for behaviour changes

2.1.1 City sustainable mobility challenges

European cities are challenged to effectively contribute to climate and environmental targets regarding CO₂ emissions, air quality, pollutants, and noise from urban mobility while, at the same time, ensuring a balanced development and use of transport options. A core objective is to enable and encourage the necessary shift from using fossil-fuel vehicles towards more sustainable mobility modes.

Cities have actively engaged stakeholder organisations and individual citizens in the development of Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans (CH4ALLENGE 2016; Rupprecht Consult 2019). But the question remains whether large numbers of citizens switch from using fossil-fuel vehicles to more sustainable mobility modes such as low-carbon public transport and active mobility (walk, cycle). There is still a large dominance of fossil-fuel car use in everyday urban mobility (Eurostat 2023).

It appears that an increasing awareness of climate change, environmental and health issues alone does not motivate many citizens to adopt sustainable mobility options. This suggests that the increasing investments of cities in more sustainable transport systems and modes needs accompanying measures that effectively promote required changes of mobility preferences. The high use of mobile devices (smartphones, tablets) and increasing familiarity of citizens with mobile applications allows ways of using digital methods to steer citizens towards adopting more sustainable mobility behaviours.

2.1.2 Digital nudging as a behaviour change approach

Cities face the challenge of promoting sustainable mobility to reduce CO₂ emissions, improve air quality, reduce noise, and thus make the city a more liveable place. To achieve this, cities can use “hard” measures such as limited traffic zones, car-free streets, congestion charges, parking space removal or increase of parking fees (Kuss & Nicholas 2022) or apply “soft” methods such as digital nudging to motivate citizens to voluntarily change their mobility behaviours. The behaviour change intervention of digital nudging is a relatively low-cost method while avoiding political issues associated with unpopular “hard” measures.

Effects of regulatory and infrastructural measures on mobility choices have been extensively studied (e.g., Kuss & Nicholas 2022; Panter et al. 2019; Vale et al. 2016). Actions addressing preferences on the demand side so far mostly inform people about negative effects of certain

choices (e.g., individual car use) which could be avoided using instead environment-friendly mobility modes such as public transport, cycling or walking.

However, there is a growing awareness among urban transport managers that informational campaigns do not lead to sustained mobility changes. This is confirmed by research that has consistently shown that informational nudges are the most accepted by citizens, but also the least effective (Sunstein et al. 2018a/b).

Digital nudging has been proposed for promoting pro-environmental behaviour in different domains (e.g., Beermann et al. 2022; Byerly et al. 2018; Grilli & Curtis 2021; Zimmermann et al. 2021), with concepts and experiments also in the field of urban mobility. Building on the wide use of and possibilities offered by smartphones, there have been considerable efforts to foster citizens' sustainable mobility behaviour through digital nudging.

Various approaches have been designed, prototyped and trialled, including informational campaigns, recommendations, challenges, game-like methods, among others (e.g., Anagnostopoulou et al. 2020; Bothos et al. 2015; Cellina et al. 2019; Di Dio et al. 2020, Klieber et al. 2020; Pajarito & Gould 2017). A review by DyMoN researchers analyzed 26 urban mobility apps which promote one or more sustainable mobility modes (e.g., walking, bicycling, use of public transport and other options) identifying the most common behaviour change methods implemented in such apps (Luger-Bazinger et al. 2023).

Researchers have criticized a lack in the mobility field of grounding (digital) behavioural interventions in a valid scientific understanding of human behaviour change (e.g., Andersson et al. 2018; Möser & Bamberg 2008; Sunio & Schmöcker 2017). A major concern is that interventions which are not firmly rooted in theoretical models of behaviour change do not enable reliable insights on barriers and enablers of target behaviour. This includes that interventions should consider the situation in which people receive nudges, regarding use of active mobility or public transport for example factors such as weather, proximity to public transport stations, traffic situation, among others.

The DyMoN digital nudging approach builds on a solid theoretical model of behaviour change and takes account of situational factors, i.e., supports situation-aware nudging.

2.1.3 The DyMoN nudging approach

Theoretical foundations of the DyMoN nudge design

DyMoN suggests using for the design of sustainable mobility nudges the transdisciplinary COM-B model together with the extensive Behaviour Change Technique Taxonomy (BCTT) (Michie et al. 2011, Michie et al. 2013; West & Michie 2020). The reasoning behind this choice is elaborated in the DyMoN deliverable "Nudging Review" (DyMoN 2022).

The COM-B model proposes that a specific behaviour "*will occur only when the person concerned has the capability and opportunity to engage in the behaviour and is more motivated to enact that behaviour than any other behaviour*" (West & Michie, 2020). Therefore, the key elements of the COM-B model, as its acronym suggests, are Capability, Opportunity and Motivation that are interacting to generate Behaviour. Figure 31 shows the COM-B model with an example of how considering the COM elements could lead to using a bicycle instead of the car for a commute to work.

Figure 31. The COM-B Model (Michie et al. 2011), adapted with an example for sustainable mobility.

Capability concerns the individual person's ability, both psychological and physical, to perform the relevant behaviour. Opportunity describes factors in the environment of the person which make the behaviour possible or support it (e.g., environmental context and resources, social approval). Opportunity is not necessarily in the person's control, for example, living in an area with good public transport or bicycle routes. Motivation relates to motivational processes of decision-making, including emotional and reflective responses to a behaviour change intervention.

All three COM elements influence behaviour and can thus be used for behaviour change interventions. For designing interventions the Behaviour Change Technique Taxonomy (BCTT) (Michie et al., 2013) offers a set of 93 different techniques for influencing behaviour that are grouped into 16 categories.

The usefulness of the COM-B model and BCTT for implementing behaviour change techniques has been demonstrated in different domains, including health care, physical activity, nutrition, saving of resources (energy, water), among others. In addition to providing useful tools for designing nudges, the COM-B model and BCTT can also be used for classifying and analyzing behavioural interventions in the field of mobility (e.g., Arnott et al. 2014; Brecht et al. 2022).

Although the relevance of the COM-B model and BCTT for mobility behaviour change interventions has been recognized soon (e.g., by the review of Arnott et al. in 2014), so far these are not widely adopted in the field. Examples are Arden et al. (2022) for an active mobility intervention based on participants' self-commitment to walk or cycle at least one of the local journeys they make each week instead of using their car; Dođru (2021) for messages promoting cycling of students, and Krusche et al. (2022) for public transport messaging of crowding information during the COVID-19 pandemic.

The DyMoN Nudging Repository

The DyMoN nudging approach based on the COM-B model and the Behaviour Change Technique Taxonomy (BCTT) has been used to design a Nudging Repository. The Nudging Repository is a set of possible digital, situation-aware behaviour change techniques and related nudge messages that can be sent via a mobile app to citizens promoting use of sustainable mobility modes, specifically, walking, bicycling and use of public transport.

The Nudging Repository contains 166 different nudges that are characterized by mobility mode, trip purpose (leisure, commuting), behaviour change category, specific behaviour change technique, situational factors, nudge text, timing, and general use (when a nudge can also be used not linked to specific situational data). Specific behaviour change techniques for

example include action planning (e.g., a sustainable mobility trip), information about consequences (e.g., positive health or environmental effects), social comparison (e.g., information on what others do), prompts/cues (e.g., reminders to keep using sustainable mobility modes), among many others.

DyMoN (2023a) provides a detailed description of the Nudging Repository and the full set of nudges is available as well (DyMoN 2023b).

Using situation-aware nudges

Researchers have noted that taking account of situational aspects, i.e., in which context a nudge reaches a person, can be crucial for successful nudging. Dixit et al. (2017) emphasize that mobility behaviour change studies require validity regarding external situations either through realistic simulation in laboratory experiments or, preferably, actual trials in the field, of which few are included in their review.

Anagnostopoulou et al. (2018) reviewed several in-field studies and found that aspects such as seasonality, weather conditions, and actual availability and accessibility of sustainable mobility options are often not considered. Javaid et al. (2020) analyzed reviews of the individual, social and infrastructural dimensions of mobility mode choice and found that all three dimensions interfere, but infrastructural aspects such as public transport network coverage or available bike lanes best explain differences in mode choice.

This means that interventions to shift mobility mode choice towards “green” options are appropriate and likely more effective in target contexts with available sufficient infrastructure and other factors such as weather conditions. For instance, nudges for promoting walking will hardly work if the walkability of the environment is poor (lack of sidewalks, heavy motorized traffic, etc.). However, instead of taking full account of such external situational factors a tendency of digital nudging has been trying to collect ever more data about the users and their mobility behaviour via their smartphones, i.e., user tracking and profiling to possibly improve the nudging.

The DyMoN project took account of the strong relation of mobility behaviour and various situational factors and developed a framework for triggering nudges in a situation-aware way, while minimizing the demand for personal data and avoiding user tracking and profiling.

To enable this approach, DyMoN has brought together in a “Data Hub” static data (e.g., mobility infrastructure) and real-time environmental data (e.g., current weather and forecast, traffic situation). (Loidl et al. 2023) The “Data Hub” allows connecting the current GPS location information of users of a smartphone app with such data that define their immediate contextual situation, for example, considering the users’ proximity to public transport stops, cycling routes, weather forecast, and other data. Based on the identified contextual situation and user preferences regarding sustainable mobility mode/s the DyMoN system can select appropriate nudges from the Nudging Repository and send these situation-aware notifications to the users of the smartphone app.

In this approach user data is kept minimal and not stored by the DyMoN system but on the users’ smartphones. The key data the system needs for providing nudges is a user’s sustainable mobility preferences and location when connecting with the system. But this data is deleted after sending the nudge notifications, i.e., there is no tracking or profiling of the user’s mobility behaviour. The DyMoN approach has been successfully applied in a functional proof of concept (Loidl et al. 2023) and in a pilot demonstration with commuters in the City of Salzburg, the results of which are presented in this deliverable.

2.2 DyMoN recommendations: themes and stakeholders, structure and overview

The DyMoN policy recommendations are based on a review of the literature and the project's own empirical research and experiences. Recommendations given by other sustainable mobility projects have been considered, however, most of these are more generic or do not relate to digital methods for promoting behaviour changes (e.g., CIVITAS-ELEVATE 2023; CIVITAS SATELLITE 2020: 29-33; PASTA 2017: 22-23; SaMBA 2018: 36-39).

In the elaboration of the recommendations, we found that it is most practical to group them under important themes rather than particular stakeholders addressed.

2.2.1 Main themes

The DyMoN recommendations are grouped under four main themes relevant for initiatives that aim to use digital methods for promoting behaviour change towards sustainable urban mobility. Related to each theme there are some topics which are important in this context.

Table 5: Overview of main themes and related topics of the recommendations.

Main themes	Related topics
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainable urban mobility policies and plans 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Sustainable urban mobility goals, policies and plans ○ Participation of citizens, businesses and civil society organisations ○ Sustainable mobility infrastructure and services and promotion of usage
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Behaviour change techniques for sustainable mobility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nudging as behaviour change intervention ○ Use of behaviour change techniques and situation-aware nudging ○ Individual and community benefits of sustainable mobility modes
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ICT and data services for behaviour change 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Digital services for behaviour change interventions ○ Data required for situation-aware nudging ○ Clear responsibility for the services involved in nudging
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legal and ethical aspects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Personal data protection, compliance with legal regulations ○ Co-creation of nudges with citizens ○ Transparent goals and means of nudging

2.2.2 Stakeholders addressed

The DyMoN recommendations are meant for five groups of stakeholders:

- City policy makers
- Citizens, civil society organisations and businesses
- City mobility services managers
- External service providers (e.g., ICT)
- Researchers

Obviously some topics and recommendations are more important to one group of the stakeholders rather than others, although the latter may still be needed to carry out the activity suggested by a recommendation. For example, while city governance is of course the realm of policy makers, the governance will not work without involving the citizens. Or, as another example, providing a mobile app to support mobility behaviour change will not work if citizens are not willing to use the app.

2.2.3 Structure of the recommendations

The DyMoN policy recommendations are structured as follows:

- The recommendations are grouped under four main themes,
- Each theme is introduced by thematic background information and literature references,
- For each theme there is a set of recommendations, introduced by stating which main stakeholder groups are addressed,
- A recommendation comprises of the recommendation statement (what is suggested) and a brief explanation of why the suggested activity is important, appropriate approaches or means, etc.

2.2.4 Overview of the recommendations

The DyMoN project focused on behavioural methods for supporting sustainable mobility policies and plans of cities. The behaviour change methods, applied with digital technologies, are intended to promote citizens' use of sustainable mobility modes, including active mobility (walk, bike) and public transport.

The DyMoN policy recommendations are based on a review of the literature on related topics and the project's own empirical research and experiences. The recommendations focus on the themes of city policies and plans for sustainable mobility, behaviour change methods for promoting use of sustainable mobility modes, supporting ICT and data services, and related legal and ethical issues.

Sustainable urban mobility policies and plans

Recommendations for all groups of stakeholders, particularly related to the development and implementation of a Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan (SUMP). Obviously in the context of city governance the stakeholders policy makers and city managers of mobility services have a leading role:

- Rec. 1: Embed and strengthen sustainable mobility in city mobility policies and plans
- Rec. 2: Ensure appropriate involvement of citizens, local businesses and civil society organisations
- Rec. 3: Give special attention to active mobility to achieve environmental and health benefits
- Rec. 4: Combine improvements of sustainable mobility infrastructure and services with behaviour change methods to promote their usage

Behaviour change methods for sustainable mobility

Recommendations for city services managers and external providers of services for behaviour change interventions, including researchers and developers of interventions:

- Rec. 5: Use behavioural interventions to advance the shift towards sustainable mobility
- Rec. 6: Select appropriate digital nudging methods for city sustainable mobility initiatives
- Rec. 7: Highlight positive effects of sustainable mobility for the individual citizen and the community

ICT and data services for behaviour change

Recommendations for city and external providers of ICT and data services for promoting sustainable mobility behaviours:

- Rec. 8: Use ICT-based services for digital nudging of sustainable mobility behaviour
- Rec. 9: Take account of what citizens expect from an application that supports sustainable mobility behaviour
- Rec. 10: Make clear to the users who is responsible for the digital nudging service and city information and physical services
- Rec. 11: Improve the availability and access to data required for supporting sustainable mobility plans and behaviour change initiatives

Legal and ethical aspects

Recommendations for city and external providers of digital services for promoting sustainable mobility behaviours, and citizens who use such services:

- Rec. 12: Ensure full compliance of the digital services with personal data protection regulations
- Rec. 13: Implement personal data protection by design and by default
- Rec. 14: Involve citizens in the design of appropriate digital nudges
- Rec. 15: Use only behaviour change methods that are acceptable in the context of public policy and services

2.3 Sustainable urban mobility policies and plans

This theme concerns challenges of cities that can be addressed with policies and plans for improved sustainable mobility and supported with behaviour change methods.

2.3.1 Thematic background

Cities are challenged to effectively contribute to climate and environmental targets regarding emissions of Greenhouse Gases (GHG), air quality, pollutants and noise from motorized vehicles while, at the same time, ensuring a balanced development and use of transport modes. Facing these challenges, a core objective for cities is to enable and encourage the necessary shift towards sustainable mobility modes, i.e., active mobility (walk, cycle) and public transport instead of using private motorized vehicles, particularly fossil-fuel vehicles.

This objective is often included in Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans (SUMP) which cities currently develop or are already implemented and monitored (EU Urban Mobility Observatory³; Kiba-Janiak & Witkowski 2019; Rupprecht Consult 2019). A SUMP is a strategic plan designed

³ EU Urban Mobility Observatory: Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans, https://urban-mobility-observatory.transport.ec.europa.eu/sustainable-urban-mobility-plans_en

to satisfy the mobility needs of citizens and businesses in a city and its surroundings with a focus on sustainable mobility. Development of such a plan encourages cross-department coordination of city management and involvement of citizens, civil society organisations and businesses (CH4ALLENGE 2016; Giorgiutti 2020; SHAPE-IT 2014; on involvement with digital tools see DYN@MO 2014; Münster et al. 2017).

More sustainable mobility of citizens has several advantages at public and individual level, including positive impacts on environment and climate, citizen health, less traffic congestion and increased safety (ARUP 2016; Netherlands Institute for Transport Policy Analysis 2018; Pisoni et al. 2022). However, there still is a much potential for increasing the take-up of sustainable mobility in cities.

Taking cycling as an example, a SUMP should foresee a combination of measures, including appropriate infrastructure and services (e.g., cycling routes, safe road crossings, bicycle parking stations) as well as promotion of their usage. Improvement in infrastructure and services alone may not be sufficient to boost cycling, while behaviour change interventions in the absence of these will not be effective and indeed questionable, e.g., regarding the safety of cyclists. Both good cycling infrastructure and services as well as behavioural motivation are necessary.

A concern that is often raised when promoting cycling is that this could lead to negative effects of air pollution and road traffic accidents suffered by cyclists. However, there is ample evidence that the health benefits of cycling greatly outweigh such risks (e.g., De Hartog et al. 2010; Mueller et al. 2015; Teschke et al. 2012). Nevertheless, cities could often do more to make streets safer for cyclists, encouraging more people to use a bicycle to commute and for leisure activities. Bicycle-friendly cities will also benefit from the “safety in numbers” effect, i.e., cycling gets safer the more people do it (CTC 2009; Jacobsen et al. 2015).

Regarding the motivation to cycle more instead of using the car, initiatives can build on car drivers own dissatisfaction due to congestion, difficulty to find a parking place, etc., while cyclists are generally more satisfied with their active travel mode (Ettema et al. 2016; Willis et al. 2013). Research has also shown that many urban car journeys are shorter than five kilometers (e.g., 43% in seven cities studied by Raser et al. 2018), while cycling is often the most suitable mode for such short distance transport. Thus, there is much potential for switching to this active mobility mode, in addition to walking for even shorter distances.

2.3.2 Recommendations

The recommendations that follow are intended for all groups of stakeholders, particularly when considered in the development of a SUMP or mobility related goals of a Smart City plan. Obviously in the context of governance city policy makers and managers of mobility services have a leading role.

Rec. 1: Embed and strengthen sustainable mobility in city mobility policies and plans

A city sustainable mobility plan enables the implementation and governance of policy-driven and integrated measures regarding urban mobility choices. In addition to public transport active mobility should be embedded and play a core role in the plan, so that measures for a walkable and bicycle-friendly city are integrated with other measures to improve city mobility solutions (e.g., multi-modal transport).

Rec. 2: Ensure appropriate involvement of citizens, local businesses and civil society organisations

Involve citizens, local businesses and civil society organisations in the definition and monitoring of measures for sustainable mobility, so that their needs and own contributions are considered.

Rec. 3: Give special attention to active mobility to achieve environmental and health benefits

Cities should make active mobility (walking, cycling) an attractive choice for citizens. Active mobility contributes to achieving environmental goals (e.g., reduction of GHG emissions, air pollution, noise) while, at the same time, it supports public health and a liveable city. Therefore, where appropriate, active mobility modes should be prioritised in urban mobility policies and plans.

Rec. 4: Combine improvements of sustainable mobility infrastructure and services with behaviour change methods to promote their usage

A city sustainable mobility plan should include a combination of improvements of sustainable mobility infrastructure and services (e.g., public transport offer, available cycling routes, improved walkability) and effective promotion of their usage. These should go together as improvements of infrastructure and services alone may not be sufficient to boost the use of sustainable mobility options. Researchers with expertise in behaviour change methods can advise on how to nudge citizens towards using sustainable options.

2.4 Behaviour change methods for sustainable mobility

This section addresses general aspects of using behaviour change methods for promoting sustainable mobility, while the application of information and communication technologies (ICT) and data for such interventions (digital nudging) is covered in greater detail in the next section.

2.4.1 Thematic background

In recent years the use of behaviour change methods to steer citizens towards more sustainable, environment-friendly and healthy behaviours (“nudging”) has become a thriving field of research. The approach of “nudging” has also been made popular among policy makers through initiatives and reports by the World Bank (2015, 2017), the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD 2017), the European Commission’s Joint Research Centre (JRC 2016), the Nordic Council of Ministers (2016), and national governments and agencies. The reports describe many examples of the nudge approach in different areas such as public health, energy and water saving, waste reduction, including some in the field of sustainable mobility (for this area see also Mont et al. 2014: 54-61).

A common understanding among researchers and policy makers is that nudging allows to influence citizens’ behaviours with “soft” and low-cost methods instead of “hard” regulations such as laws, bans or taxes. Hard measures are often difficult to implement as these require political negotiation and overcoming resistance by affected parties, for example, when trying to restrict car use in city areas.

Instead of applying coercive measures nudging aims to influence citizens so that they change behaviours voluntarily, for example, use active mobility modes to contribute to making the city a more pleasant place to live and work and benefit regarding personal health and well-being (Netherlands Institute for Transport Policy Analysis 2018; Pisoni et al. 2022).

A nudge basically is a recommendation to citizens together with information that both motivates and helps them follow the suggested behaviour, which is seen as beneficial for the wellbeing of the individuals as well as the community. In practice a variety of nudging techniques is being used, ranging from changes in the physical environment, e.g., narrowing the side-lines on a road to get drivers to slow down, to information-based digital methods such as enabling people to compare their energy consumption to those of others (see the overview of methods in Section 2.7: Appendix).

DyMoN focused on motivational methods using digital tools (e.g., a smartphone app) for promoting behaviour change towards using sustainable mobility modes (walk, cycle, public transport). Various motivational techniques have already been used for this purpose, including for example information and education about environmental benefits of adopting sustainable mobility modes, promoting in trip planning the selection of the most sustainable option, tracking and providing feedback on mobility behaviour (e.g., carbon footprint of trips), gamification, comparison of the results of participants, and providing rewards for using sustainable mobility modes (Luger-Bazinger et al. 2023 provide an analysis of the methods used in 26 urban mobility apps).

The DyMoN framework goes beyond most current approaches by using behaviour change techniques in combination with situation awareness. This is enabled by the innovative DyMoN Nudging Repository that uses an individual’s location and situational context data (e.g., weather, traffic situation, proximity to public transport stops, cycling routes, etc.) to select and send via a mobile app the most relevant nudge messages to promote use of sustainable mobility modes (for more information on situation awareness and required data see the Sections 2.1.3 and 2.5).

The DyMoN Nudging Repository contains 166 different nudges that are characterized by mobility mode (walk, cycle, public transport), trip purpose (leisure, commuting), behaviour change technique, situational factors, nudge text, timing, and general use (when a nudge can also be used not linked to specific situational data). The behaviour change techniques for example include action planning, information about consequences (e.g., emotional, health, environmental), social comparison, prompts/cues, among many others.

The repository of digital nudges is available free and open access and can be used by researchers, city or external service providers and other organisations, working with a mobile application, to select or add nudge messages for promoting the use of sustainable mobility choices in different contexts.

Which nudging techniques and messages to apply will depend on the user's goals and focus of the mobile application, trip planning or health and wellness activities, for instance. A more recent trend are challenges and competitions for sustainable mobility where the app allows participants to compare their results to those of others (Di Dio et al. 2020; Klieber et al. 2020; Pajarito & Gould 2017). This approach belongs to the social influence techniques, e.g., use of social norms and social comparison. These can play an important role in promoting sustainable mobility, taking account of the fact that behaviours are often influenced by social approval and support by relatives, friends or colleagues.

2.4.2 Recommendations

The recommendations that follow are intended mainly for city mobility managers, external providers with a focus on sustainable mobility, researchers and developers of behaviour change interventions promoting sustainable mobility.

Rec. 5: Use behaviour change interventions to advance the shift towards sustainable mobility

Behaviour change interventions allow cities to influence citizens' behaviours with "soft" and low-cost methods instead of "hard" regulations such as laws, bans or taxes. Instead of applying coercive measures nudging aims to influence citizens so that they change behaviours voluntarily, for example, use active mobility modes instead of the car, thereby avoiding effects such as GHG emissions, air pollution and noise.

Rec. 6: Select appropriate digital nudging methods for city sustainable mobility initiatives

The high usage of mobile devices (smartphones, tablets) and increasing familiarity of citizens with mobile applications allow using digital nudging to steer citizens towards adopting more sustainable mobility behaviours. Cities can select from different possible nudging techniques, e.g., information and education on benefits of sustainable mobility, feedback on mobility behaviour (e.g., carbon footprint of trips), gamification and comparison of the results of participants, among others.

Rec. 7: Highlight positive effects of sustainable mobility for the individual citizen and the community

Behaviour change initiatives should highlight the contributions sustainable mobility of citizens makes to city goals regarding the environment, public health, and a liveable city in general. For example, cycling can improve the health and well-being of citizens and, at the same time, make the city a more pleasant place to live and work.

2.5 ICT and data services for situation-aware nudging

This section addresses the use of information and communication (ICT) services and data sources for digital behaviour change interventions with a focus on situation-aware nudging for sustainable mobility (walk, cycle, public transport). The data sources concern data for situation awareness such as available mobility infrastructure and services, traffic situation, weather, and other conditions relevant for using sustainable mobility modes, while personal data and its protection is addressed in the next section.

2.5.1 Thematic background

ICT services for motivating behaviour changes

The high usage of mobile devices (smartphones, tablets) and increasing familiarity of citizens with mobile applications allows novel ways of using digital approaches to steer citizens towards adopting more sustainable behaviours. These approaches can apply basic nudging methods such as information and education as well as more engaging ways of supporting behaviour change such as gamification.

Use of ICT applications to influence behaviours with digital nudging has been suggested by several researchers and for different societal and environmental domains (e.g., Caraban et al. 2019; Hummel & Maedche 2019; Jesse & Jannach 2021; Karlsen & Andersen 2019; Meske & Potthoff 2017; Mirsch et al. 2017; Schneider et al. 2018; Weinmann et al. 2016). Various digital nudging techniques have also been trialled for promoting sustainable urban mobility (e.g., Anagnostopoulo et al. 2018; Andersson et al. 2018; Bothos et al. 2015; Cellina et al. 2019; Di Dio et al. 2020).

Use of digital nudging requires a platform to organise and run the activities and an app for the participants. These are needed for user registration and participation, i.e., receiving notifications (alerts, reminders), guidance and encouragement to carry out proposed activities.

Meurer et al. (2019) interviewed citizens to understand what they expect from an application that supports sustainable urban mobility. The researchers found that citizens wish information on how such mobility is measured and monitored, respect for individual mobility situations and preferences, the expected scope of participation, and the sharing of responsibility between citizens and city services.

Nudging platforms are usually provided by ICT organisations external to city administrations which prefer to focus on applications in their public-service remit. Therefore, it is advisable that a platform which supports behavioural interventions (e.g., a competition promoting cycling) is clearly separated from city information services (e.g., a GIS-based city map of cycling routes) and of course the physical services (e.g., the actual cycling routes). But these areas are intertwined as the behavioural interventions via the nudging platform are intended to increase the use of the city infrastructure and services for sustainable mobility.

This constellation requires being very clear about who is responsible for which service, i.e., city services versus external services, and related tasks and responsibilities such as personal data protection.

Data services required for situation-aware nudging

For situation-aware nudging of sustainable mobility behaviour it is necessary to understand the user context, particularly via data on the current user location and data on various situational factors external to the user such as weather, traffic situation, proximity to public transport stops or cycling routes, among others.

Understanding the user context is key to providing innovative services (Coutaz et al. 2005). Consequently, context recognition has become a fast field of research and development, for

example, to develop smart city services, including mobility services (see the reviews Capurso et al. 2018; do Nascimento et al. 2021; Pacheco Rocha et al. 2022; and Weiser et al. 2016 with a focus on supporting sustainable mobility).

The DyMoN approach of situation-aware nudging has been developed following this line of research but avoids issues of extensive collection of data about the users' behaviours from their mobile devices, e.g., for user tracking and profiling. Instead, the DyMoN approach focuses on data on factors external to the users that are relevant for choosing sustainable mobility options and provides motivational nudges to do so. Data about external factors, for example, include available infrastructure dedicated to pedestrians and cyclists, proximity to public transport stops and their accessibility, current traffic conditions, real-time weather information and forecast.

A functional proof of concept demonstrated that the DyMoN approach is feasible (Loidl et al. 2023) but in addition to open access data (e.g., OpenStreetMap, weather data) had to use proprietary licensed data (e.g., traffic situation), proxy variables as well as apply special models and data processing (e.g. for calculating walkability and bikeability of areas). Thus, situation-aware nudging currently must deal with considerable limitations regarding availability and access to adequate datasets.

A further push for required datasets on national open data platforms, including city-level data, could support and improve data-driven applications for sustainable mobility behaviour. One driver here is the EU Directive on Open Data and the Re-use of Public Sector Information (Directive 2019/1024) which also lists relevant types of high-value *datasets* the availability and accessibility of which should be improved.

Another driver, supported by the European Commission, is the development of Data Spaces for data pooling and sharing with a focus on private data of businesses and other organisations (Beverungen et al. 2022; European Commission 2022). The initiative includes Data Spaces for mobility data, e.g., the Mobility Data Space in Germany⁴ and others on the Data Spaces Radar of the International Data Spaces Association (IDSA)⁵.

In this context cities aiming to plan and promote sustainable mobility are well-advised to optimize their data collection and integration strategies for effective decision-making on suitable measures and solutions (CIVITAS-ELEVATE 2023: 10-11). This can include collecting necessary mobility data, bringing together data already held by public departments and agencies, and data sharing agreements with private partners. Cities may also seek to integrate mobility related data and make it available to public and private stakeholders on a city open data platform or as part of a national open governmental data platform.

2.5.2 Recommendations

The recommendations that follow are intended mainly for city and external providers of ICT and data services for promoting sustainable mobility behaviours.

Rec. 8: Use ICT-based services for digital nudging of sustainable mobility behaviour

Use of digital nudging to promote sustainable mobility of citizens requires an ICT-based platform to organise and run the activities and an app for the participants. These are needed for user registration and participation, i.e., receiving notifications (alerts, reminders), guidance and encouragement to use sustainable mobility options.

⁴ Mobility Data Space (MDS), <https://mobility-dataspace.eu>

⁵ IDSA: Data Spaces Radar, <https://internationaldataspaces.org/adopt/data-spaces-radar/>

Rec. 9: Take account of what citizens expect from an application that supports sustainable mobility behaviour

Providers of an application that supports sustainable mobility with digital nudging should take account of what citizens expect from such an application, e.g., information about how sustainable mobility is measured and monitored and respect for individual mobility situations and preferences.

Rec. 10: Make clear to the users who is responsible for the digital nudging service and city information and physical services

Digital nudging services are usually provided by ICT organisations external to city administrations which prefer to focus on applications in their public-service remit. Therefore, it should be made clear to users who are responsible for the nudging services and who for the city information and physical services (e.g., a GIS-based city map of cycling routes and the physical routes).

Rec. 11: Improve the availability and access to data required for supporting sustainable mobility plans and behaviour change initiatives

Cities should optimize their data collection and integration strategies to effectively support a sustainable mobility plan and promote sustainable mobility, including with situation-aware behaviour change interventions. This will require collecting necessary mobility data, bringing together data already held by public departments and agencies, and data sharing agreements with private partners. Available data could be made accessible on a city open data platform or as part of a national open governmental data platform.

2.6 Legal and ethical aspects

This section addresses legal requirements when providing digital services to support sustainable behaviours, particularly personal data protection, and ethical aspects of behaviour change methods.

2.6.1 Thematic background

Compliance with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

When using digital services to promote behaviour changes a major legal issue to address is the protection of personal data. In the member states of the European Union the General Data Protection Regulation (Regulation [EU] 2016/679), short GDPR, is the core legal framework in this regard (European Union 2016). Digital platforms and apps cities or supporting external service providers are using to promote active mobility should fully comply with the rules set by the GDPR.

The regulation is quite complex, however, the main rule to follow is that users of the digital services should give informed consent regarding the use of the personal data they provide for the purposes of the services. A minimum age is necessary to give informed consent which should not be below 13 years (e.g., in Austria it is 14 years).

Users will have to register and provide personal information (e.g., e-mail address, mobile phone number, etc.) so that they can use the services and be informed about the progress of activities in which they participate. The personal data should not be disclosed to third parties or, if shared with other services, provided only in anonymized or pseudonymized form, so that the identity of the citizen cannot be inferred from the data (e.g., in pseudonymization personally identifiable data is replaced with artificial identifiers).

Digital service providers should generally not collect and process any sensitive personal information as defined in Article 9 of the GDPR such as data “revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person’s sex life or sexual orientation”.

Service providers must of course also put in place appropriate technical, organizational and procedural measures to ensure data protection and security. The ways data are being processed must be described in a Record of Processing Activities and, in case of a formal complaint, the document provided to the national Data Protection Agency.

Personal data protection by design and by default

Article 25 of the GDPR maintains that personal data protection and privacy principles are best adhered to when they are already integrated in the technical setup of data processing systems (“data protection by design”) and only data are collected and processed which are necessary for the specific purpose of an application (“data protection by default”), e.g., data minimization, short storage period, no or only legitimate access by third parties.

The DyMoN approach of situation-aware nudging provides an example of adhering to these principles (Loidl et al. 2023). In this approach nudges for sustainable mobility are delivered via a smartphone user app as notifications. The app is also used for collecting data about the user where necessary, but this data is not kept on a central server. Instead, personal data is exclusively stored on the users’ devices.

Communication between the user app and the DyMoN Data Hub is managed in a system interface which sends a request to the app, which returns user preferences regarding

sustainable mobility and current location information. With this, the interface queries the Data Hub and returns adequate nudges, if available, for the specific situation of the user. The location information is packed into the request URL and not stored server-side. To ensure privacy, temporary user IDs, which are deleted every day, are used for communication between the user app and the system interface.

Thereby the communication was designed for minimized and anonymized personal data and no such data was conveyed to the Data Hub. Consequently, the approach does not apply tracking of user mobility behaviour based on GPS location data or user profiling based on other personal data. Instead, a useful service supporting sustainable mobility can be achieved through the situation-aware nudging.

Addressing ethical issues

Ethical issues in nudging mainly concern the behaviour change methods digital platforms and apps can employ to nudge citizens towards certain choices and behaviours. In the literature nudging is debated because methods can be used which are not transparent and exploit psychological processes with the effect that people take decisions in a non-reflected, quasi-automatic way (Hansen & Jespersen 2013; Hausman & Welch 2010; Ivanković & Engelen 2019; Sunstein 2015).

The appropriate approach to avoid ethical concerns is to use only methods that are transparent regarding the aims (e.g., increase cycling of citizens instead of using the car) and means (e.g. a competition with rewards to promote that behaviour). More background on which methods are appropriate is given in the Appendix on nudge types and ethics.

Luger-Bazinger et al. (2022) of the DyMoN project team discuss the design of digital nudges from the perspective of responsible innovation. They see great potential of digital nudging to motivate behaviour changes for the greater good, e.g., acting against climate change through sustainable mobility, but also that nudging can generate potential friction. Therefore, it is important to design and use nudges in ways so that citizens feel included, comfortable and secure. This concerns both the very nature of nudging as well as the use of personal data, which may be used for the personalization of nudge messages.

Luger-Bazinger et al. (2022) suggest using co-creation workshops and methods to involve citizens in the design of nudges, explain the concept of nudging and give examples, receive ideas and feedback of citizens on appropriate and useful nudges, and take account of their needs and apprehensions. The result should empower citizens through transparent nudging, information about how personal data is being used to generate nudges, and other aspects of nudging important to citizens.

2.6.2 Recommendations

The recommendations that follow are intended for developers and providers of digital services that support sustainable behaviours, and citizens who use such services.

Rec. 12: Ensure full compliance of the digital services with personal data protection regulations

Digital platforms and apps cities or supporting external service providers use for promoting sustainable mobility should fully comply with the personal data protection regulations that are in force. In the member states of the European Union the General Data Protection Regulation (Regulation [EU] 2016/679) is the core legal framework in this regard. In particular, users of the digital services have to give informed consent regarding the use of the personal data they provide for the purposes of the services.

Rec. 13: Implement personal data protection by design and by default

Personal data protection and privacy principles are best adhered to when they are already integrated in the technical setup of the data processing systems (“data protection by design”), for example, avoiding collection of personal data wherever possible. Only personal data should be collected and processed which are necessary for the specific purpose of an application (“data protection by default”), e.g., data minimization, short storage period, no or only access by legitimate third parties.

Rec. 14: Involve citizens in the design of appropriate digital nudges

It is essential to design and use sustainable mobility nudges in ways so that citizens feel included, comfortable and secure. Therefore, it is advisable to involve citizens in the design of such nudges (e.g., organize co-creation workshops). This allows to explain the concept of nudging and give examples, receive ideas and feedback of citizens on appropriate and useful nudges, and take account of their needs and apprehensions. The result should empower citizens through transparent nudging, information about how personal data is being used to generate nudges, and other aspects of nudging important to citizens.

Rec. 15: Use only behaviour change methods that are acceptable in the context of public policy and services

Ethical issues when applying digital behaviour change methods to promote sustainable mobility can be avoided by enabling citizens to take a well-informed decision regarding the use of such methods and supporting tools. The appropriate approach for this is to use only methods that are transparent regarding the aims, e.g., a campaign aimed to increase cycling instead of using the car, and the means, e.g., a competition promoting that behaviour. Researchers and practitioners in sustainable mobility promotion should be aware of the legal and ethical requirements of appropriate digital nudging.

2.7 Appendix: Nudge types and ethics

Use of nudging in DyMoN

DyMoN explored the feasibility of digital situation-aware nudges to promote sustainable mobility behaviour of citizens. Nudges aim to steer individuals towards behaviours which are deemed preferable for the wellbeing of people and society, for example, cycling instead of using the car to improve health conditions and avoid environmentally negative effects.

In the literature nudging is debated as potentially unethical because methods can be used that are not transparent and exploit psychological processes with the effect that people take decisions in a non-reflected, quasi-automatic way (Hansen & Jespersen 2013; Hausman & Welch 2010; Ivanković & Engelen 2019; Sunstein 2015).

In DyMoN none of these methods have been employed. The methods used are transparent regarding the aims and the means that are being employed. The overall aim is to foster sustainable mobility behaviour of citizens (i.e., walk, cycle, use public transport), and the core means are situation-aware nudges that use digital messages which promote such behaviour, taking account of situational aspects such as weather conditions, traffic situation, availability of public transport, cycling routes, among others.

Distinguishing between different types of nudges

Nudges use different techniques to steer the decision-making of people in a particular direction or affect behaviours directly. Characteristics of these techniques provide the basis to distinguish different types of nudges and to evaluate whether these are appropriate in ethical terms.

In the discussion of nudges researchers and practitioners often refer to two distinctions which characterize the techniques that are being employed:

- if the techniques address “System 1” (automatic) or “System 2” (reflective) cognitive processes, and
- if the techniques work in a Transparent or Non-transparent way.

We briefly explain the distinctions “System 1” / “System 2” and Transparent / Non-transparent, and then use a matrix of these distinctions to discuss the different types of nudges. Thereafter we explain where the methods are positioned which have been used in DyMoN.

System 1 (automatic) versus System 2 (reflective)

The two systems theory of cognitive processes has been developed by Kahneman (2003, 2011). According to this theory the human brain works in two different ways:

- “*System 1*”: processes information fast, uncontrolled and effortless in a quasi-automatic way,
- “*System 2*”: processes information slow, controlled and effortful in a reflective way.

It is assumed that people make most judgements and choices of daily life quasi-automatically, i.e., without really making a reflected conscious decision. Automatic here means based on cognitive biases, heuristics and mental shortcuts, while reflective involves following rules of logical thinking, weighing the costs and benefits of various options, or other ways to arrive at a well-considered decision.

Transparent versus Non-transparent

The distinction refers to the intention as well as the means employed in a nudge:

- *Transparent*: the intention is clear, and people are made aware or can easily identify the means employed to influence their decision-making or behaviour,
- *Non-transparent*: the intention is not disclosed and how a certain decision or behaviour change is pursued remains hidden.

Obviously nudges with non-transparent conditions combined with triggering System 1 (automatic) cognitive processes are highly manipulative, while addressing System 2 (reflective) transparently regarding the intention and means appears as a legitimate way of trying to persuade citizens to take a particular decision or change a behaviour.

Matrix of types of nudges

Hansen & Jespersen (2013) combined the two distinctions in a matrix that allows grouping and evaluating different types of nudges. Table 6 presents the matrix, in which we include techniques that are often used for certain types of nudges, and examples from the literature (e.g. Hansen & Jespersen 2013; Nordic Council of Ministers 2016; Stanak & Winkler 2015).

Table 6: Matrix of types of nudges, adapted from Hansen & Jensen (2013)

	System 1 (automatic) <i>Nudge affects behaviour directly</i>	System 2 (reflective) <i>Nudge affects choice directly</i>
Transparent <i>(by design)</i>	<p>Transparent influence of behaviour</p> <p><u>Techniques:</u> Typically in the form of a technical manipulation</p> <p><u>Examples:</u> Car alarms for seat belts Provide larger household recycling than waste bins Change printer defaults from one-side to double-sided printing</p>	<p>Transparent facilitation of choice</p> <p><u>Techniques:</u> Provide information, education and guidance</p> <p><u>Examples:</u> Nutritional labelling of food products Information that most people pay their taxes in time (social norm) Comparison of own energy consumption to those of other people (social comparison)</p>
Non-transparent	<p>Non-transparent manipulation of behaviour</p> <p><u>Techniques:</u> Change the environment (physical arrangements and/or objects) in which people make choices</p> <p><u>Examples:</u> Narrow the side-lines on a road to get drivers to slow down Eliminate cues for smoking by keeping cigarettes and ashtrays out of sight Provide smaller plates in self-service restaurants to reduce food waste</p>	<p>Manipulation of choice</p> <p><u>Techniques:</u> Various techniques, e.g. salience, framing, priming, default opt-in</p> <p><u>Examples:</u> Making one option more salient than the alternative (salience) Framing one decision as involving a potential loss (activating people's loss aversion) Default opt-in, where one must actively opt-out to prevent enrolment in a programme</p>

An important general aspect is that nudges addressing “System 1” are intended to influence behaviours directly while “System 2” nudges concern decision-making.

“*System 1*” – *transparent nudges* typically come in the form of a technical manipulation and are warning people (e.g., car alarms for seat belts), while “*System 1*” – *non-transparent nudges* aim to change people’s behaviour by changing the environment of choices (e.g., re-ordering the food in a canteen so that the healthier options are presented first).

“*System 2*” – *transparent nudges* are clear regarding the objective and means, where the latter typically is informing people (e.g., nutritional labelling of food products). “*System 2*” – *non-transparent nudges* address people’s reflective system but are not fully clear about the means that are being employed to influence the decision-making (e.g., most people will not know about psychological effects of a default opt-in).

Evaluation of nudging methods employed in DyMoN

The nudging methods which have been used in DyMoN to promote the use of sustainable urban mobility options (walk, cycle, public transport) belong to the “System 2” (reflective) transparent methods. These methods encourage people to take a well-informed decision and change behaviours, for example, based on information about positive effects on health and the environment (e.g., reduced CO₂ emissions, air pollution and noise) and support in planning the use of sustainable mobility options.

“System 2” (reflective) transparent methods can facilitate deliberate and reasoned decision-making by citizens. Therefore, these methods are the least debated forms of nudging and generally seen as ethically appropriate ways of trying to persuade citizens to take a particular decision and change behaviours (Hansen & Jespersen 2013; Hausman & Welch 2010; Ivanković & Engelen 2019; Lin et al. 2017). Also surveys on citizen’s opinion about different nudges show that the public supports these methods with much higher approval rates than other proposed forms of nudging (Reisch & Sunstein 2016; Sunstein et al. 2018a/b).

3 Policy Briefing

Dynamic Mobility Nudge: Shaping sustainable urban mobility behaviour with real-time, user generated and public open data (DyMoN)

Policy briefing

DyMoN project, January 2024

Cities are challenged to effectively contribute to climate and environmental targets regarding CO₂ emissions, air quality, pollutants, and noise from urban mobility. The DyMoN project proposes that cities use digital nudging to promote more sustainable mobility of citizens (i.e., walk, cycle, public transport). The project developed and trialled a novel approach of such nudging that applies behaviour change techniques in combination with situation awareness. Such awareness considers the users' proximity to cycling routes, public transport stops, traffic situation, weather forecast, and other available data. The DyMoN recommendations concern city policies and plans for sustainable mobility, behaviour change methods for promoting use of sustainable mobility modes, supporting ICT and data services, and related legal and ethical issues. Stakeholders in sustainable mobility addressed are city policy makers, managers of mobility infrastructure and services, providers of other services (e.g., behavioural intervention methods, ICT and data services), and citizens who use such services.

Introduction

Cities face the challenge of promoting sustainable mobility to reduce CO₂ emissions, improve air quality, avoid pollutants and noise, and thereby make the city a more liveable place. A core objective is to enable and encourage the necessary shift from using fossil-fuel vehicles towards more sustainable mobility modes, i.e., walking, cycling, using public transport. To achieve this, cities can use "hard" measures such as congestion charges, car-free streets and removal of parking space or apply "soft" methods of nudging to steer citizens towards voluntarily changing their mobility behaviours.

The high use of mobile devices (smartphones, tablets) and increasing familiarity of citizens with mobile applications allow using digital nudging methods to motivate citizens to adopt sustainable mobility behaviours. The behaviour change intervention of digital nudging is a relatively low-cost method while avoiding political issues associated with unpopular "hard" measures. However, use of digital nudging to shift mobility mode choice towards "green" options requires sufficient sustainable mobility infrastructure and services to be appropriate.

The DyMoN approach of situation-aware nudging

Digital nudging has been proposed for promoting sustainable behaviours in different fields, including urban mobility. Various behaviour change techniques have already been applied, e.g., informational campaigns, social norms, mobility challenges and other game-like methods, among others.

The DyMoN project developed and trialled an innovative approach that allows using such methods in combination with situation awareness. The approach takes account of the fact that the situation

in which a nudge reaches a person can be crucial for a successful behavioural intervention. Regarding the promotion of sustainable mobility choices situational factors, for example, include weather, traffic situation, proximity to public transport stations or cycling routes.

DyMoN created a “Nudging Repository”, a set of 166 different nudges that are characterized by mobility mode (walk, cycle, public transport), trip purpose (leisure, commuting), behaviour change technique, situational factors, nudge text, timing, and general use (when a nudge can also be used not linked to specific situational data). The behaviour change techniques include action planning (e.g., a sustainable mobility trip), information about consequences (e.g., positive health or environmental effects), social comparison (e.g., information on what others do), prompts/cues (e.g., reminders to keep using sustainable mobility modes), among others.

To enable situation awareness, DyMoN has brought together in a “Data Hub” various data on situational factors as mentioned above. The “Data Hub” allows connecting the current GPS location information of users of a smartphone app with such data that define their immediate situation. Based on the identified situation and user preferences regarding sustainable mobility mode/s the DyMoN system can select appropriate nudges from the Nudging Repository and send these situation-aware notifications to the users of the smartphone app.

A tendency in digital nudging has been trying to collect ever more data about the users and their mobility behaviour via their smartphones to possibly improve the nudging through user tracking and profiling. Instead, the DyMoN approach uses situational factors external to the user to support sustainable mobility choices while minimizing the demand for personal data. The key data the DyMoN system needs for providing nudges is a user’s sustainable mobility preferences and location when connecting with the system. But this data is deleted after sending the nudge notifications, i.e., there is no tracking or profiling of the user’s mobility behaviour.

The DyMoN approach has been successfully applied in a functional proof of concept and in a pilot demonstration with commuters in the City of Salzburg.

DyMoN recommendations

The DyMoN policy recommendations are based on a review of the literature on related topics and the project’s own empirical research and experiences. The recommendations focus on the topics of city policies and plans for sustainable mobility, behaviour change methods for promoting use of sustainable mobility modes, supporting ICT and data services, and related legal and ethical issues. Stakeholders in sustainable mobility addressed are city policy makers, managers of mobility infrastructure and services, providers of other services (e.g., behavioural intervention methods, ICT and data services), and citizens who use such services.

Sustainable urban mobility policies and plans

- Rec. 1: Embed and strengthen sustainable mobility in city mobility policies and plans
- Rec. 2: Ensure appropriate involvement of citizens, local businesses and civil society organisations
- Rec. 3: Give special attention to active mobility to achieve environmental and health benefits
- Rec. 4: Combine improvements of sustainable mobility infrastructure and services with behaviour change methods to promote their usage

Behaviour change methods for sustainable mobility

- Rec. 5: Use behavioural interventions to advance the shift towards sustainable mobility
- Rec. 6: Select appropriate digital nudging methods for city sustainable mobility initiatives
- Rec. 7: Highlight positive effects of sustainable mobility for the individual citizen and the community

ICT and data services for behaviour change

- Rec. 8: Use ICT-based services for digital nudging of sustainable mobility behaviour
- Rec. 9: Take account of what citizens expect from an application that supports sustainable mobility behaviour
- Rec. 10: Make clear to the users who is responsible for the digital nudging service and city information and physical services
- Rec. 11: Improve the availability and access to data required for supporting sustainable mobility plans and behaviour change initiatives

Legal and ethical aspects

- Rec. 12: Ensure full compliance of the digital services with personal data protection regulations
- Rec. 13: Implement personal data protection by design and by default
- Rec. 14: Involve citizens in the design of appropriate digital nudges
- Rec. 15: Use only behaviour change methods that are acceptable in the context of public policy and services

Detailed thematic background of the recommendations is given in a project deliverable (see below DyMoN 2024).

Project identity

Project name: Dynamic Mobility Nudge: Shaping sustainable urban mobility behaviour with real-time, user generated and public open data (DyMoN)

Duration: May 2021 – April 2024

Consortium: Salzburg Research Forschungsgesellschaft mbH, Salzburg, Austria – project coordinator

University of Salzburg, Department of Geoinformatics, Austria

Trafficon – Traffic Consultants GmbH, Germany

Uppsala University, Department of Civil and Industrial Engineering and Built Environment, Sweden

Sustainability InnoCenter, Sweden

Ecollective, Sweden

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Website: www.dymon.eu

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- Further reading: DyMoN (2024). Evaluation of pilot demonstrations and policy recommendations & briefing. Project Deliverable D2.2a, January 2024. Available in Zenodo, <https://zenodo.org/communities/dymon/>
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